

Review of Zero Waste Pattern Making Techniques in Building Sustainable Fashion

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Abstract:

The fashion industry is creating major environmental concerns by polluting the water, increasing the use of natural resources, and creating landfills with textile and apparel waste. Due to fast fashion, there has been an increase in apparel production and textile waste. During the manufacturing process of apparel, converting the 2D patterns to 3D shapes involving, cutting, sewing, finishing, fusing, and the rest of the process, 15% of total fabric consumption goes into waste and creates a landfill. Fabric wastes exist in Pre-consumer textile waste and post-consumer textile waste. Pre-consumer textile waste includes wastes created from yarn development to fabric and garment development. Post-consumer textile waste is created out of consumer-used apparel. It is the need of the hour that the industry must take appropriate conscious action to build an eco-friendly environment.

Zero-waste Pattern Making, a part of Zero waste fashion design, is one technique that utilizes the fabric's width, leaving no textile waste or minimizing the textile waste. All the methods of Zero waste pattern making aim at maximizing the complete width of the fabric and reducing the fabric waste. This paper focuses on the available methods of Zero waste pattern making and reviews the technique, its technicality, outcomes, challenges, and possibilities associated with zero-waste pattern making.

The objective of this study is to bring the focus of the industry to this option of zero waste pattern-making technique, to achieve a sustainable environment, reviewing the techniques and finding the possibilities of opportunities in Zero waste patternmaking. The methodology used is descriptive using secondary data, reviewing the research articles focusing on Zero waste fashion design and zero-waste pattern-making techniques, set of practices, rules and principles, and explorations. Analysis of the literature review will help researchers, academicians, and industry to find the direction and opportunities in zero waste pattern making.

Keywords: *Fashion Design, pattern making, Pre-consumer textile waste, Sustainable Fashion, Zero waste*

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1. Introduction

Sustainability has become an integral part of our lives. According to UN 1987, sustainability is meeting the needs of today without compromising the next generation's capability of meeting their needs. Sustainable development takes care of environmental concerns along with economic growth [1].

Sustainable Fashion aims to achieve a carbon-neutral fashion based on equality, animal welfare, ecological integrity, and social justice. Sustainable Fashion not only focuses on textiles and products, its process, entire product lifecycle including consumption and disposal. Fast fashion is following trends and producing affordable fashion at a rapid speed for consumers. Consumers buying the same and disposing off more to follow the trends, creating a throwaway culture as per the sustainability experts. Enormous clothing production due to Fast Fashion and Throwaway culture is creating a landfill of Textiles and apparel waste [2].

The rise of Fast Fashion has led to a surge in apparel production, contributing to an alarming increase in textile

waste. Throughout the apparel production process, which encompasses the cutting of 2D patterns in fabric and their assembly into a 3D structure through sewing, finishing, fusing, and other techniques, approximately 15% of the total fabric used ends up as waste in landfills, posing significant environmental concerns. This fabric waste takes two forms: Pre-consumer textile waste, involving the wastage in yarn, fabric, and garment production, and post-consumer textile waste, which includes discarded garments after consumer use.

Addressing this environmental issue, Zero Waste Fashion Design (ZWFD) emerges as a sustainable fashion approach that combines various techniques to utilize fabric efficiently, minimizing waste during garment creation. A key component of ZWFD is Zero Waste Pattern Cutting, encompassing methods such as subtraction cutting, transformational reconstruction, precision cutting, jigsaw puzzle, tessellation, draping, multiple cloth approach, minimal cut, seamless knitting, layer method, direct panel on loom (DPOL), geo cut, all aimed at reducing the fabric waste and few maximizing the complete width of fabric. In this design paradigm, the designer plays a crucial role, taking the lead in designing garments while considering fabric width and ensuring the entire width is utilized, thereby promoting a more sustainable and eco-friendly fashion production.

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1.1 Background

Timo Rissanen identified the three methods of creating fashion considering textile waste – Fully fashioned, cut and sew, and A-POC. This categorization is mostly based on the fabric construction, which is woven, knit, and non-woven. Fully Fashioned focuses mostly on knitting, where the garment shapes/patterns are knitted individually and then linked or sewn together [3]. With the design changes, knitting a new panel through the knitting machine can be a bit of an expensive process hence knitwear is mostly a combination of fully fashioned and cut & sew. A rectangular panel is knitted then through cut and sewing methods attached to each other with a regular knitted seam. An advanced version of the fully fashioned garment is seamless knitting which has always been present in the system since 1990 for complex garments like socks, and gloves. In seamless knitting, the complete garment is knitted without the seam and avoids the cut-and-sew method in the process. Even examples of non-woven and woven have been mentioned by Timo Rissanen for fully fashioned garments, where the mention of molded plastic bodice by Issey Miyake from 1980 is one of them [4]. Looms generally develop the rectangular straight length of fabric, although shaped woven pieces can be created through handloom as demonstrated by Burnham [5]. Technology related to Weaving shapes through looms do exist and one of the few examples is, the development of fully fashioned woven products for the medical industry by a German company as per research published in shape3 [6]. DPOL (Direct Panel on Loom) developed by an Indian designer also one of the examples of fully fashioned garments with woven fabric where the woven shapes are created through a loom and later stitched utilizing cut and sew approach and creates no fabric waste [7].

In 1990 Japanese designer Issey Miyake and his colleague Dai Fujiwara launched the technique A-POC (A piece of cloth) where the yarn is knitted or woven to create fabric tubes which creates a cavity hole in between. Black explained the difference between the A-POC and Seamless Knitting as A-POC does the warp knitting and seamless knitting involves weft knitting using the computer to guide the knitting machine [8]. A tube-like structure of fabric is created where the fabric waste is determined by how the customer is cutting the fabric. As per Timo Rissanen, the A-POC technology is inventive yet not achievable by most manufacturers.

Cut and Sew method is the mostly used method by the manufacturers, where the pattern pieces are cut and then sewn together. It can be applied to woven, knitted or non-wovens, and is a widely used method. Textile manufacturers are mostly developing fabric meant for cut and sew methods. With this method, during the process of garment making, fabric waste generated is prominent and can vary for different kinds of garments. Adult outerwear can create 10-20% waste while using cut and sew methods [9]. For pants and jeans waste generation can be 10% and a high range for blouses, undergarments and jackets [10]. According to Coolkin the

average fabric waste generated through cut and sew method is 15% of the total fabric used [11].

In this paper, Zero Waste Pattern Making refers to the cut-and-sew method where there is no fabric waste or minimal fabric waste. Pattern pieces get interlocked to each other, utilizing the width of fabric, and creating no waste unlike A-POC, fully fashioned or cut-and-sew methods [3].

1.2 Objective

- To understand the Zero Waste Pattern Making (ZWPM) technique in the global and Indian apparel sector (Secondary Review).
- To review the challenges and adaptability of ZWFD techniques with emphasis on Pattern Making technique
- To bring the focus of the industry to this option of zero waste pattern-making technique
- To achieve a sustainable environment, reviewing the techniques and finding the possibilities of opportunities in Zero waste pattern making.
- To understand the different available techniques in zero waste pattern making and all aspects of zero waste technique that have been explored.

2. Methodology

A literary analysis of research conducted in between 2013–2022. The employed keywords in the research were zero waste fashion design and zero waste pattern making, with the intention to investigate the zero-waste pattern making techniques explored. This review only selected research papers, journals, papers which spoke about the techniques of zero waste pattern making. It doesn't include the history, historical garments and techniques, manufacturing and zero was pattern making and CAD and zero waste pattern making. Concentrates only around the techniques related to pattern making and draping.

3. Literature Review

Zero waste pattern making practices initiate at the design stage of apparel. With different ways of achieving no waste during the Pattern cutting and sewing stage, various practice-based methods have been adopted by different designers and have created a nomenclature for Zero Waste Fashion Designers.

3.1 Tessellation

Design practice includes repeating one shape, multiple times to fit together and create a design, leaving no gaps within the shapes. A Dutch artist M.C Escher is popular for his complicated tessellation, highlighting fish, birds and lizards. McQuillan's exploration in tessellation explains an intentional approach to create an outcome by fitting the shell-like curved shapes together to mold around the fashion figure and creating an aesthetically nice and textured outcome [13]. McQuillan's intentional approach for tessellation exploration was not mass friendly as the shape has round

edges and to utilize the fabric till selvages, a straighter edge is required. McQuillan's tessellation exploration was pinned not stitched as per the body shape and was not at par with the utilization of fabric, it needed to reduce the scale of shapes to fit against the selvage and further reduce the gap against the selvage as seen in Figure 1 [14]. Carla Fernandez's Chamula garment exhibited in the YEILD exhibition, worked on the tessellation technique, utilizing the triangles for skirts and rectangles and other needed shapes to create the body, this leads in utilizing the complete width of fabric with the different shapes as visible in Figure 2 [13].

Figure 1: McQuillan Intentional Approach to Tessellation

Figure 2: Carla Fernandez's Chamula Garment

3.2 Jigsaw Puzzle & Embedded Jigsaw Puzzle

Very well practiced by Holly McQuillan and Timo Rissanen, follows the traditional set of pattern-making shapes, except they are placed in width of fabric, as per keeping the zero waste in mind. In a Jigsaw puzzle the concave curve of one pattern piece can be included in the convex curve of another pattern piece, complimenting each other, one part of garment is adjusted to another part of garment. It can be applied to any kind of garment following the traditional patterns. In the jigsaw method, whatever is added to one part of the garment shape, the same is removed from another part of the garment shape, which is not the case in the traditional pattern-cutting method. The designer using the jigsaw puzzle method focuses on 1 style of garment whereas in the Embedded Jigsaw puzzle, McQuillan suggests an efficient way of

creating zero waste fashion by creating multiple styles, instead of one [12]. Creating zero waste fashion by including 1 garment fabric waste to another garment. Compared to tessellation where a particular shape is repeated, embedded jigsaw and jigsaw puzzle has freedom to use the traditional pattern shapes [12].

3.3 Multiple Cloth Approach

Defined by McQuillan is a method 'to design two or more patterns for different fabrics at the same time' [12]. This technique may be convenient for mass production as multiple styles are designed in 1 marker plan. As authors practiced was not based on producing multiple garments, Multiple Cloth Approach couldn't be conducted by them [15].

3.4 Minimal Cut

Zero-waste fashion design is a sustainable tool for producing apparel products. The outcome of the technique is eco-friendly to the environment. A focus on a holistic methodology where the designer along with the pattern maker together creates an aesthetic yet functional outcome. Carrico and Kim practiced Holly McQuillan 4 design shaping sustainable fashion technique, tessellation, jigsaw puzzle, embedded jigsaw and multiple cloth approach, utilizing these techniques he developed his own designs and proposed the 5th design practice, minimal cut which focus on draping the whole cloth with minimal cutting and utilizing the whole width of fabric [16].

3.5 Subtraction cutting

An innovative approach invented by Julian Roberts focuses on the negative space within the garment instead of focusing on the outer edge of the garment. The approach concentrates on achieving creative shapes, with the help of big fabric sheets, cutting shaped holes through which the body passes through, using fast and imprecise cutting methods which are not based on critical mathematical calculations as seen in Figure 3. The garments achieved through subtraction cutting can be defined as adventure and discovery. Julian Roberts, red and white dress is a combination of 2 fabric sheets, red and white. The garment can be worn and presented in 5 different ways, hence achieving 5 different looks customers are achieving through their single buy, achieving zero waste fashion [13].

Figure 3: Subtraction Cutting by Julian Roberts

Figure 4: Exploration of fitted garments through TR

3.6 Transformational Reconstruction (TR)

Exploration on Transformational Reconstruction (TR) has been highlighted and a practice-based study was done. Application of TR, which is an innovative pattern making technique, has been observed within Zero Waste framework. Usually contemporary methods create 15% waste, utilizing and by changing the basic contemporary women's wear silhouette, 3 apparel designs have been explored with the help of Jigsaw puzzle and TR technique to reduce the textile waste and observe the figure-flattering fit. TR cutting utilization considering the zero waste mostly produces fitted garments as visible in Figure 4. An integrated working has been highlighted where pattern making and cutting process combined into design progression, evoke the designer to think 3D than 2D. The final look of the garment is mostly predictable. Cloth utilization becomes efficient and decreases the environmental impact of energy loss and material feed for forming the textile, also the transportation increased cost and discarding fabric waste [17].

3.7 Surgery Cutting and Pattern anatomies, exploring 3D shaping techniques

Comparison and collaboration of pattern cutting, and surgery cutting is discussed through practice-based research and paper suggested an attractive methodology of shape making for Fashion Design which is inspired by surgery cutting. Investigation on surgery cutting to compare with fashion design started in 2013 through practice-based research and explorations on scale, repetition, mirror imaging and placement of these techniques as the 'Triangular

transposition' and 'the advancement flap' used in surgery cutting, suggests movement and added elasticity of skin. Common practices have been observed between surgery and pattern cutting, like skin has longer lines to follow for cut and cloth has grainline to follow for cut. For preparation, surgeons draw on the body and designers draw on body form to start with the designs. Based on the similarities, an extraordinary starting point has been observed for 'bias cut' explorations. Early surgical methods were designed in 1920-30 and around that time only bias-cut explorations for fit in Fashion Design have been explored and a strong connection was advised to be established between the surgery and pattern cutting. It has been suggested to investigate the connection between surgical and pattern cutting and merge with the current zero waste aesthetics as the surgical cutting is known for zero waste technique. A practice based two-week research, collaboration at Nottingham Trent University July 2020, has been published through a short film named A pattern Anatomies. Collaboration of surgeons and designers highlighted with some old common findings and new exploration. Being zero waste and shape-making were the focus keeping the movement and fit theme while the collaboration of two different contrast fields. Pattern Anatomies came up with the technique where the shaping was formed through the making of flaps and movements of flaps within the fabric. The possibility of making the garment without cutting away fabric waste and with the transmission of the flaps takes us to two dimensional to three-dimensional shaping techniques. The film concentrates on the response received on exploring each other's way of cutting technique,

shaping, fitting, movement, and achieving zero waste options. The paper highlights the interdisciplinary collaboration to achieve zero waste, understanding a surgeon's cutting technique, training and exploring, and achieving a common language of cutting techniques in the Fashion Fraternity [18].

3.8 Simple Cutting and slashing method

Utilizing the waste by adding the value in the garment can be another strategy which has been discussed where a practice led research has highlighted that a simple cutting and slashing method can add value to the apparel and initiate fresh different opportunities in the Fashion and apparel production process. The designer used the scraps to add aesthetic value to the garment or to add added fullness in her garment through gussets, godet etc. The research suggests zero waste as a tool of sustainable fashion and supports that it can be applied to the fashion industry and mass production is possible [14].

3.9 DPDC (Design, Pattern Making, Draping and Cutting)

Origami folds of paper translated into fabric led to a fascinating finding regarding the forming and wearability and achieving production and commercial motives related to textile waste. A new method to remove textile waste during the cut and sew process is a combination of design, pattern making, draping, cutting, and including zero waste method forming a synthesis together in 1 piece of fabric. The integrated technique is named DPDC which includes Design, Pattern Making, Draping and Cutting. An open-source library has been offered for the creative community, which reduces fabric waste during the sewing time. Most of the times, DPDC works on fabric width, the width of the fabric defines the garment size, throwing insights to customers into how the garments are being made. With this technique, a garment can be worn in multiple ways as seen in Figure 5. Different fabric widths will give different outcomes on a single body type. Since the technique follows origami, once the garment is worn completely, later the garments shapes can be opened back to the original square or rectangular shape of the fabric [19].

Figure 5: Paper House and slash and arrange dress develop through DPDC

3.10 Incision Cutting

Inspired by the linear cutting methods in Indian traditional garment, which was almost zero waste, following the geometric shape of the pattern pieces leaving no negative space, led Kalra, J. explored and founded a new technique

Incision Cutting Technique focusing on sustainability and adaptability of chikankari craft of India. Technique focuses on minimum cut, creating different shapes and gussets, inspired from the traditional Indian garment, kali kurta as visible in Figure 6 & 7. Kalra, J also highlighted how the traditional seaming technique, which itself is zero waste seaming technique, can be used as an ornamental seaming solution to garment. Daraz is a hand done application of flat and felled seam, in which the seam allowance is shaped in beautiful creepers and motif and sewn from both the sides [20].

Figure 6: Incision Cutting by Jaspal Kalra

Incision technique is the combination of straight piece of body fabric, a straight armhole incision into the straight piece of fabric and straight piece sleeve insertion to the straight armhole.

Figure 7: Incision Cutting by Jaspal Kalra

4. Conclusion

Zero waste pattern making techniques can be grouped in 4 sections, Creative Techniques, Mass production-friendly techniques, Draping, and Simple pattern-making techniques. Creative Zero Waste Pattern Making Techniques focus on explorative and adventurous pattern techniques that focus on zero waste pattern making. Subtraction cutting focuses on negative space within the garment and achieves an unexpected silhouette and outcome which itself is an adventurous discovery. Transformational Reconstruction (TR) focuses on 3D garment than 2D pattern and efficient fabric is being utilized by maintaining the fit of the garment. An interdisciplinary comparison and study based on zero waste-oriented surgery cutting led to a direction that which achieving zero waste through pattern cutting can be

achieved. 'Triangle Transposition' and 'Advancement Flap' suggest the movement of flaps and lead to 3D shaping technique.

Mass production-friendly techniques could be, Jigsaw Puzzle, Embedded Jigsaw, and Multiple Cloth Approach technique. The papers reviewed suggested them to be production-friendly and embedded jigsaw and multiple cloth approach focuses on more than one style. Techniques derived from simple and traditional pattern making techniques are focusing on slashing and cutting methods, achieving zero waste through godet, gussets and adding value through scraps. Following the linear cutting method of Indian traditional Kalidar kurta, which is almost zero waste, Incision cutting has been defined where incision of sleeve and body happen with the help of gussets, all pieces are in geometric shapes. Tessellation is repeating a particular shape, if it has a straight edge, is easy to utilize the complete width of fabric, and comes under the simple geometric pattern repeating itself. Any other shape than the straight edge is still a challenge to utilize the complete width of the fabric.

References

- [1] United Nations, 'Sustainability | United Nations' [Internet] [n.d.]. <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/sustainability#:~:text=In%201987%2C%20the%20United%20Nations,to%20meet%20their%20own%20needs.%E2%80%9D>
- [2] Chugh, S., "What is Sustainable Fashion? Why Does it Matter and How to Achieve it." Emeritus Online Courses [Internet]. [updated 7th March 2024; published 9th January 2023], <https://emeritus.org/blog/sustainability-sustainable-fashion/>
- [3] Rissanen, T., 'Zero-waste fashion design: A study at the intersection of cloth, fashion design and pattern cutting', OPUS, (May, 2013), <http://hdl.handle.net/10453/23384>
- [4] Fukai, A. & Suoh, T., "Fashion: The collection of the Kyoto Costume Institute: a history from the 18th to the 20th century", Taschen, Köln & London. (2002)
- [5] Burnham, D. K., 'Cut My Cote', Textile Department, Royal Ontario Museum, (1973). <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB02923891>
- [6] Shape 3, 'Seamless woven 3D shells directly out of the loom' (n.d.). http://shape3.com/FrameSet_Shape3.htm
- [7] Xue, Z., & Huang, Z., "Current Development and Future Prospects of Designing Sustainable Fashion". Autex Research Journal/Autex Research Journal, 23(3), 420–431, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.2478/aut-2022-0013>
- [8] Black, S., 'Knitwear in Fashion from 1970', In Bloomsbury eBooks, (2015b). <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474260428-fpa202>
- [9] Feyerabend, R., "Textiles Briefing Paper", viewed February 5, 2007, (2004). <<http://www.mrs-hampshire.org.uk/Workshop%204/Textiles.pdf>>
- [10] Abernathy, F.H., Dunlop, J.T., Hammond, J.H. & Weil, D., "A stitch in time. Lean retailing and the transformation of manufacturing - Lessons from the apparel and textile industrie", Oxford University Press, New York & Oxford, (1999)
- [11] Cooklin, G., Hayes, S. G., McLoughlin, J., & Fairclough, D., 'Cooklin's Garment Technology for Fashion Designers', John Wile & Sons. (2011). https://openlibrary.org/books/OL29105036M/Cooklin's_Garment_Technology_for_Fashion_Designers
- [12] Gwilt, A., & Rissanen, T., 'Shaping Sustainable Fashion'. Routledge. (2012). http://books.google.ie/books?id=_tMZ6k0Zr90C&printsec=frontcover&dq=Zero-waste+design+practice:+Strategies+and+risk+taking+for+garment+design.&hl=&cd=2&source=gbs_api
- [13] McQuillan H., Rissanen T., 'Yield: Making fashion without making waste' [Exhibition] The Dowse Art Museum, New Zealand, (2011). <https://hollymcquillan.com/design-practice/yield-making-fashion-without-making-waste/>
- [14] Pingki, M. J., "An experiment to create Zero Wastage Clothing by stitching and slashing technique". International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, 10(10), 1283–1290, (2019). <https://doi.org/10.14299/ijser.2019.10.06>
- [15] McQuillan, H., "Zero-waste design practice: Strategies and risk taking for garment design", (2011)
- [16] Carrico, M., & Kim, V., "Expanding zero-waste design practices: a discussion paper." International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education, 7(1), 58–64. (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543266.2013.837967>
- [17] Saeidi, E., & Wimberley, V. S., "Precious cut: exploring creative pattern cutting and draping for zero-waste design". International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education, 11(2), 243–253, (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543266.2017.1389997>
- [18] Sissons J., "Pattern Anatomies: Can surgery cutting inform zero-waste fashion design?" [Conference Paper Presentation], Global fashion Conference, (2020), https://gfc-conference.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/SISSONS_Can-surgery-cutting-inform-zero-waste-fashion-design.pdf
- [19] Sharma, Pragya, "ZERO WASTE: EXPLORING ALTERNATIVES THROUGH FOLDING", the Learning Network on Sustainability, (2021), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351549407_ZERO_WASTE_EXPLORING_ALTERNATIVES_THROUGH_FOLDING
- [20] Kalra, J., "Zero Waste Fashion A field research on Design with Chikankari Artisans." Cumulus Mumbai 2015' in a Planet of Our Own'. (n.d.). https://www.dsource.in/sites/default/files/resource/planet-our-own-papers-2015/contents/file/11_Jaspal_Kalra-Cumulus_Mumbai_2015.pdf